

The leaf beetles (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) of the Pirin Mountain (Bulgaria)

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GRUEV B. 2006. The leaf beetles (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) of the Pirin Mountain (Bulgaria).
- *Historia naturalis bulgarica*, 17: 51-79.

Abstract. The paper reviews the diversity of leaf beetles of Pirin Mts, South Bulgaria. Two-hundred and eighty nine (sub)species are hitherto registered on the territory of the mountain (of them 38 are new records), which counts to approx. 57 % of the Bulgarian chrysomelid fauna. Of them, six species (*Clytra valeriana tetrastigma*, *Luperus graecus*, *Gonioctena pallida reticulata*, *Oreina speciosissima drenskii*, *O. virgulata ljubetensis*, *Aphthona parnassicola*) are Balkan endemics, and one (*Longitarsus behnei*) is local endemic. The dominant zoogeographical complexes are: Siberian (150 taxa), and European (113 taxa).

Key words: Leaf beetles, Chrysomelidae, Faunistics. Zoogeography, Pirin Mts, Bulgaria

Introduction

The Chrysomelidae fauna of the Pirin Mountain has not been a subject of special investigations. Nevertheless, 289 species and subspecies have been established in the mountain by now (38 of them are herein newly recorded as belonging to the fauna of the mountain; asterisked in the faunistic list). That number is sizable considering that it represents 57 % of the taxa known in Bulgaria. It cannot be affirmed, however, that the faunistic composition is finally fixed. Findings of some rather more widespread species are quite possible, especially in the low parts of the mountain. It is also possible some other high mountain relicts, Mideuropean in origin, to be found (particularly representatives of *Oreina* and *Chrysolina*).

The herein-accepted west border of the Pirin Mountain is the Struma Valley, and its east border is the Mesta Valley.

Material

The faunistic list is composed on the basis of all the published data on the species in the Pirin Mountain. Many specimens from Dr. V. Tomov's and of the author's collections, are also used. An abbreviation, indicative of its zoogeographical belonging, is added to each taxon in the list. Abbreviations: excl. - excluding; incl. - including; m.h. - mountain hostel; p. - place; vill. - village.

Faunistic list

Orsodacninae

Orsodacne cerasi (Linnaeus, 1758)

Mt. Pirin, Sandanski Valley (VIG, 2002). New material: p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1250 m, 11.V.1985; m. h. "Yane Sandanski", 1200 m, 2.VI.1972.

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Orsodacne humeralis Latreille, 1804

Mt. Pirin, Sandanski Valley (VIG, 2002). New material: vill. Mesta, 17.V.1973; vill. Gospodintsi, 18.V.1973; vill. Dobrinishte, 17.V.1973. Distribution: France, south part of Mid Europe, Italy, Balkan Peninsula, Asia Minor. E\SbM\HSbM

Donaciinae

* *Donacia cinerea* Herbst, 1784

above Sandanski, 10.V.1967, 7.VI.1964. Distribution: from North-East Spain and South France to Altai. S\EAP\SsibE

Donacia impressa Paykull, 1799

vill. Delchevo (TOMOV, 1973). Distribution: from the Iberian Peninsula and Ireland to West Siberia and Mongolia. S\EAP\SibE

* *Donacia marginata* Hope, 1795

Gotse Delchev, 19.VI.1938. Distribution: Europe, Asia Minor, West Siberia, North Africa. S\EAP\SibE

* *Plateumaris consimilis* (Schrank, 1781)

Bansko, 9.VI.1987. Distribution: from West Europe to Japan. S\EAP\TrPal

Plateumaris sericea (Linnaeus, 1758)

vill. Dobrinishte, 1000 m; p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1300 m (WARCHALOWSKI, 1974), Begovitsa basin, 1900-2000 m (TOMOV, 1979). New material: vill. Lilyanovo, 9.V.1985. Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Transcaspia, Siberia, Japan. S\EAP\TrPal

Criocerinae

Lema cyanella (Linnaeus, 1758)

above Sandanski (TOMOV, 1970c). Distribution: from Spain and the British Isles to Korea. S\EAP\TrPal

Oulema gallaeciana (Heyden, 1870)

p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1400 m (WARCHALOWSKI, 1974 - *Lema lichenis*). New material: Banderitsa, 7.VI.1938; Melnik, 10.VI.1987; Bansko, 10.VI.1987. Distribution: western, northern and central parts of Europe, the whole Danube basin, European Russia, West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Oulema melanopus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Sandanski - vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (TOMOV, 1979). New material: Bansko, 1200 m, 19.VI.1972; Melnik, 13.V.1981. Distribution: from Ireland, South Norway and Morocco to the Near East, West and Middle Siberia, Mongolia. S\EAP\SibE

Clytrinae

Clytra atraphaxidis (Pallas, 1773)

Pirin Mt. (ROUBAL, 1931), Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: South and South-East Europe, Corsica, Sardinia, Caucasus, Asia Minor, West Iran, Kazakhstan, Middle Asia, Mongolia, Korea. S\EAP\TrPal

Clytra laeviuscula Ratzeburg, 1837

Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: West, Mid, South and South-East Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Middle Asia, Altai range. S\EAP\SibE

Clytra novempunctata Olivier, 1808

Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski; vill. Kremen; vill. Lopovo; Rhozenski monastery above Melnik (VIG, 2002). New material: vill. Vlahi, 20.VI.1908. Distribution: Balkan Peninsula, Romania, South Ukraine, Daghestan, Transcaucasus, Asia Minor, North-West Iran, Iraq, Turkmenistan; Sicily. SWAs\SbIn

Clytra quadripunctata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), Banderitsa Valley, 1700-1900 m (TOMOV, 1979), m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski (VIG, 2002). New material: Pirin Mountain, 2500 m, 20.VII.1984; Bansko, 1200 m, 19.VI.1972. Distribution: from North Spain and Ireland to Middle Asia and Mongolia. S\EAP\SibE

* *Clytra valeriana tetrastigma* Schmidt, 1841

Melnik, 20.VI.1986. Distribution: Greece, Bulgaria, Serbia, Macedonia. End\BnEnd

* *Coptocephala gebleri* Gebler, 1814

Gotse Delchev, 20.VII.1964; Melnik, 6.VIII.1984, 17.VIII.1982; vill. Lilyanovo, 14.VII.1979. Distribution: Balkan Peninsula, Transcaucasus, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Kirghizstan, southern Siberia, Altai. S\EAP\SibE

* *Coptocephala rubicunda* (Laichaerting, 1781)

Gotse Delchev, 20.VII.1964; m. h. "Banderitsa", 1800 m, 16.VII.1975. Distribution: Mid and East Europe; France and the Pyrenees. E\ME

* *Coptocephala unifasciata* (Scopoli, 1763)

Gotse Delchev, 20.VII.1964; Melnik, 14.VII.1972, 7.VIII.1984. Distribution: from Spain and Belgium to the Middle East, Kazakhstan, Middle Asia, Mongolia and Baikal area. S\EAP\SibE

Labidostomis cyanicornis (Germar, 1822)

vill. Mesta (TOMOV, 1970a). New material: Gotse Delchev, 11.V.1968; Bansko, 20.V.1981. Distribution: southern part of Mid Europe, Romania, Ukraine, Volga basin, Kazakhstan. E\ME

Labidostomis humeralis (Schneider, 1792)

m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 1250 m (TOMOV, 1970a). Distribution: Mid, South and East Europe, Asia Minor. E\ME

Labidostomis longimana (Linnaeus, 1761)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m; southeast slopes of Vihren peak, 2100-2350 m (TOMOV, 1979), above Razlog; Rozhenski monastery above Melnik (VIG, 2002). New material: Bansko, 15.VII.1985; Melnik, 4.VIII.1984; vill. Dobrinishte, 17.VII.1965; vill. Vlahi, VII.1932. Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Siberia, Mongolia. S\EAP\SibE

* *Labidostomis oertzeni* Weise, 1889

Melnik, 15.V.1981, 1.VI.1988. Distribution: Bulgaria, Greece, North-West Turkey. E\SbM\ESbM

Labidostomis pallidipennis (Gebler, 1830)

Melnik (WARCZALOWSKI, 1974). New material: vill. Delchevo, 22.VI.1969.

Distribution: Mid, East and South Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Siberia, China. S\EA P\SibE

Labidostomis propinqua (Faldermann, 1837)

m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 1250 m (TOMOV & GRUEV, 1965 - *Labidostomis beckeri*).

New material: Banderitsa, 14.VI.1938. Distribution: Bulgaria, South Romania, Greece, Caucasus, Asia Minor. E\SbM\ESbM

Lachmaia sexpunctata (Scopoli, 1763)

m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski; vill. Kremen; vill. Lopovo (VIG, 2002). Distribution: North-East France (Moselle basin), South Germany, Danube basin, Romania, Ukraine, Balkan Peninsula, Asia Minor. E\SbM\HSbM

Macrolenes dentipes (Olivier, 1808)

Pirin Mt. (ROUBAL, 1931 - *Miopristis dentipes*), Melnik (WARCZALOWSKI, 1974 - *Miopristis dentipes*), Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 650-700 m (TOMOV, 1970b - *Miopristis dentipes*). Distribution: South Europe, Asia Minor, North Africa. M\HM

* *Smaragdina affinis* (Illiger, 1794)

m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 3.V.1964. Distribution: England, France, Italy, Mid Europe, Bulgaria, Romania, South Ukraine, Finland. E\ME

Smaragdina aurita (Linnaeus, 1767)

m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski (VIG, 2002). New material: Melnik, 30.IV.1990. Distribution: Pyrenees, West France, Italy, Mid Europe, Caucasian countries, Asia Minor. E\ME

Smaragdina concolor hypocrita (Lacordaire, 1848)

Melnik (WARCZALOWSKI, 1974 - *Gynandrophthalma hypocrita*). Distribution: Bulgaria, Romania, Asia Minor. E\SbM\ESbM

* *Smaragdina flavicollis* (Charpentier, 1825)

Bansko, 14.VI.1938; Banderitsa, 14.VI.1938. Distribution: from France and North Italy to Ukraine and North Turkey; Lithuania, Finland. E\ME

* *Smaragdina graeca* (Lefevre, 1872)

vill. Rozhen, 15.V.1985. Distribution: southern parts of the Balkan Peninsula. E\SbM\ESbM

* *Smaragdina limbata* (Steven, 1806)

Melnik, 27.IV.1970. Distribution: Balkan Peninsula, Caucasian countries, Asia Minor, the Middle East, North Iran. SWAs\SbIn

* *Smaragdina salicina* (Scopoli, 1763)

Melnik, 12-20.V.1981. Distribution: North, South and East Europe, from North Spain and Denmark to the Volga basin; Caucasian countries. E\ME

* *Smaragdina tibialis* (Brulle, 1832)

vill. Mesta, 18.V.1973. Distribution: Balkan Peninsula, Asia Minor, Syria. SWAs\AsM

Smaragdina xanthaspis (Germar, 1824)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 300-350 m (TOMOV, 1979), Rozhenski monastery above Melnik (VIG, 2002). New material: Pirin Mountain, 1400 m, 20.VII.1984; Gotse Delchev, 3.VII.1961; Bansko, 30.VI.1969, 9.VII.1976; Melnik, 23.VI.1969, 28.VI.1982, 9.VII.1976; vill. Vlahi, VII.1932; vill. Delchevo, 22.VI.1969;

Banderitsa, 14.VI.1938. Distribution: North Italy, northern part of the Balkan Peninsula, the Danube basin, South Ukraine, Asia Minor. E\SbM\ESbM

* *Tituboea macropus* (Illiger, 1800)
Bansko, 8.VI.1984. Distribution: South-East Europe, from Austria and Albania to the Volga basin and the Caucasian countries. E\SbM\ESbM

Cryptocephalinae

Cryptocephalus apicalis Gebler, 1830
vill. Dobrinishte, 1400 m (WARCHALOWSKI, 1974). New material: Banderitsa, 13.VI.1938. Distribution: from Austria to East Siberia. S\EAP\TrPal

Cryptocephalus aureolus illyricus Franz, 1949
Begovitsa Valley, 1700-2000 m (TOMOV, 1979). New material: Bansko, 3.VI.1987, 30.VI.1969; M. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 21.VI.1969; p. "Cherna Voda, VI.1929. Distribution: Austria, Hungary, Romania, Balkan Peninsula, Slovenia. E\SbM\ESbM

* *Cryptocephalus bicolor* Eschscholtz, 1818
Bansko, 5.V.1974; Melnik, 5.V.1974; vill. Mesta, 18.V.1973. Distribution: South France, Danube basin, Bulgaria, Crimea, Caucasus countries, North Turkey, North Iran. SWAs\SbIn

* *Cryptocephalus bilineatus* (Linnaeus, 1767)
Bansko, 24.VI.1924, 16.VII.1965. Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Siberia, Korea, Japan. S\EAP\TrPal

Cryptocephalus bipunctatus (Linnaeus, 1758)
Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (TOMOV, 1979), vill. Kremen; Rozhenski monastery above Melnik (VIG, 2002). New material: Bansko, 1200 m, 9.VI.1988, 19.VI.1972; Melnik, 9.V.1988, 12.V.1981, 23.V.1970; Banderitsa, 13.VI.1938. Distribution: widely distributed from Portugal and Ireland to Korea; North Africa. S\EAP\HPal

* *Cryptocephalus chrysopus* Gmelin, 1788
Gotse Delchev, 5.V.1983; Melnik, 9.V.1985; vill. Mesta, 18.V.1973. Distribution: Mid Europe; South France, North Italy, Bulgaria, Crimea. E\ME

Cryptocephalus connexus Olivier, 1807
Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (TOMOV, 1979). New material: Gotse Delchev, 9.VII.1972; Bansko, 16.VII.1965, 20. VII. 1984; Melnik, 25.VII.1956, 7.VIII.1984. Distribution: South and East Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan. SWAs\SbIn\InTur

Cryptocephalus coryli (Linnaeus, 1758)
m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski (VIG, 2002). New material: p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 10.VI.1975. Distribution: Europe, Kazakhstan, Siberia, Korea. S\EAP\TrPal

Cryptocephalus duplicatus Suffrian, 1847
Melnik (WARCHALOWSKI 1974 - *Cryptocephalus concolor*). Distribution: eastern part of the Balkan Peninsula, Caucasus, Asia Minor. E\SbM\ESbM

Cryptocephalus elegantulus Gravenhorst, 1807
vill. Dobrinishte, 1300 m (WARCHALOWSKI, 1974), Rozhenski monastery above Melnik (VIG, 2002). New material: Bansko, 15.V.1985, 19.VI.1972, 7.VII.1987; Melnik, 11.V.1967, 23.V.1969, 23.VI.1970. Distribution: Europe, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Middle Asia, Siberia, Mongolia, Korea. S\EAP\TrPal

Cryptocephalus exiguus Schneider, 1792
vill. Rozhen (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: Europe, Asia Minor, West Siberia, Prebaikal area. S\EAP\SibE

Cryptocephalus flavipes Fabricius, 1781
Rozhenski monastery above Melnik (VIG, 2002). New material: Gotse Delchev, 5.V.1983; Bansko, 5.VI.1987; Melnik, 11.V.1967, 22.V.1984, 23.V.1970, 5.VI.1987, 23.VI.1969; vill. Mesta, 18.V.1973; vill. Lilyanovo, 10.V.1968; p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 11.V.1985. Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Middle Asia, Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

* *Cryptocephalus frenatus* Laicharting, 1781
Bansko, 22.VII.1971. Distribution: West France, Germany, Poland, Danube and Dnester basins. E\ME

Cryptocephalus hypochoeridis (Linnaeus, 1758)
p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1400-1600 m (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), Begovitsa Valley, 1400-1600 m (TOMOV, 1979). New material: Gotse Delchev, 9.VII.1972; Bansko, 30.VI.1969, 12.VII.1978; Melnik, 12.VII.1987, 6.VIII.1984; m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 21.VI.1969. Distribution: Europe, Asia Minor, South Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

* *Cryptocephalus imperialis* Laicharting, 1781
Melnik, 5.VI.1987. Distribution: North Spain, France, South Germany, Danube basin, Balkan Peninsula, Ukraine, Asia Minor. E\ME

* *Cryptocephalus janthinus* Germar, 1824
Bansko, 30.VI.1969; Melnik, 23.V.1969, 1.VI.1968; vill. Delchevo, 22.VI.1969. Distribution: Mid, South and South-East Europe, Asia Minor, Iran, Kazakhstan, Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Cryptocephalus labiatus (Linnaeus, 1761)
Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 400-450 m (TOMOV, 1979). New material: Gotse Delchev, 11.V.1968; Bansko, 16.VIII.1981; Melnik, 16.VIII.1981. Distribution: Europe, Asia Minor, Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Cryptocephalus macellus Suffrian, 1860
vill. Mesta (TOMOV, 1971). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, the Black Sea area (?Tunisia). E\ME

Cryptocephalus marginatus Fabricius, 1781
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: France, Netherlands, North Italy, Germany, South Poland, Danube basin, Romania. E\ME

Cryptocephalus moraei (Linnaeus, 1758)
Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m; Banderitsa basin, 2000-2100 m (TOMOV, 1979), m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski; above Razlog; Rozhenski monastery above Melnik (VIG, 2002). New material: Gotse Delchev, 3.VII.1961; Bansko, 24.VI.1968, 31.VII.1988; Melnik, 15.V.1981, 23.VI.1969, 31.VII.1988, 4.VIII.1984; vill. Vlaha, VII.1934; vill. Dobrinishte, 17.VII.1965; vill. Mesta, 11.V.1968. Distribution: Europe (excl. the northern part of Scandinavia). E\ME

* *Cryptocephalus nitidus* (Linnaeus, 1758)
p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 11.V.1985. Distribution: Europe, South Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Cryptocephalus ocellatus Drapiez, 1819
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (TOMOV, 1979). New material: Gotse Delchev, 11.V.1968; Bansko, 24.VI.1968, 30.VII.1969, 17.VII.1965; vill. Dobrinishte, 17.VII.1965; vill. Lilyanovo, 10.V.1968, 22.VII.1971. Distribution: Europe, Asia Minor, Iran, Kazakhstan, West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Cryptocephalus ochroleucus Stephens, 1834
Melnik (GRUEV & TOMOV, 1998). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Balkan Peninsula, North Africa. E\ME

Cryptocephalus octacosmos Bedel, 1891
Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (TOMOV, 1979). New material: Gotse Delchev, 9.VII.1972; Melnik, 20.VII.1983; vill. Delchevo, 22.VI.1969. Distribution: Mid, South and East Europe, Middle Asia, West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Cryptocephalus octomaculatus Rossi, 1790
Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (TOMOV, 1979).
Distribution: Mid and South Europe, West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Cryptocephalus octopunctatus (Scopoli, 1763)
vill. Krema (VIG, 2002). New material: Bansko, 3.VI.1987; vill. Dobrinishte, 17.V.1973. Distribution: Europe, Kazakhstan, West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Cryptocephalus parvulus Mueller, 1766
p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1300 m (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). New material: Bansko, 7.V.1972.
Distribution: Europe, Kazakhstan, Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Cryptocephalus pini (Linnaeus, 1758)
Vihren peak, 2100-2350 m (TOMOV & GRUEV, 1973).
Distribution: Europe (incl. Norway), West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

* *Cryptocephalus populi* Suffrian, 1848
Melnik. Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan. S\EAP\SibE

* *Cryptocephalus prusias* Suffrian, 1853
Rozhenski monastery above Melnik, 14.VII.1970. Distribution: eastern part of the Balkan Peninsula, Asiatic Turkey (incl. the east part: Erzurum District), Syria, Jordan. SWAs/SbIn

* *Cryptocephalus pusillus* Fabricius, 1776
Melnik, 17.VII.1976. Distribution: almost the whole of Europe. E\ME

Cryptocephalus pygmaeus vittula Suffrian, 1848
above Razlog; vill. Lopovo - *Cryptocephalus pygmaeus* (VIG, 2002). New material: Banderitsa, 9.VII.1977.
Distribution: mainly in Mid and East Europe; Caucasian countries, Asia Minor. E\ME

Cryptocephalus quadriguttatus Richter, 1820
vill. Dobrinishte, 1300 m (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: Mid, East and South-East Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Cryptocephalus querceti Suffrian, 1848
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: North and Mid Europe, southwards to the Balkan Peninsula. E\ME

* *Cryptocephalus quinquepunctatus* (Scopoli, 1763)
Gotse Delchev, 11.V.1968; vill. Mesta, 11.V.1968. Distribution: Mid South and South-East Europe. E\ME

Cryptocephalus schaefferi Schrank, 1789
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: Mid, South and South-East Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Cryptocephalus sericeus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 25-500 m (TOMOV, 1979), m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski; vill. Dobrinishte; Vihren peak, 1800 m; Rozhenski monastery above Melnik (VIG, 2002). New material: Gotse Delchev, 3.VII.1961, 20.VII.1964; Bansko, 16.VII.1965, 20.VII.1982; Melnik, 15.V.1981, 23.VI.1969, 16.VII.1982; vill. Vlaha, VI.1934, 14.VII.1961; Banderitsa, 14.VI.1938. Distribution: Europe, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Siberia, North-West China. S\EAP\SibE

Cryptocephalus solivagus Leonardi et Sassi, 2001

m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 1200 m (VIG, 2002). Distribution: East Europe, ?Finland, Turkey, Iran, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Siberia, Altai. S\EAP\SibE

Cryptocephalus strigosus Germar, 1823

p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1400 m (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). New material: Bansko, 1200 m, 19.VI.1972. Distribution: North Italy, Balkan Peninsula, Danube basin. E\SbM\ESbM.

Cryptocephalus trimaculatus Rossi, 1790

Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), Rozhenski monastery above Melnik (VIG, 2002), Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 400-450 m (TOMOV, 1979). New material: Gotse Delchev, 20.VII.1964. Distribution: southern part of Europe, from South France and Italy to Hungary and the Balkan Peninsula; Asia Minor, Near East. E\SbM\HSbM

* *Cryptocephalus turcicus* Suffrian, 1847

Melnik, 11.V.1967, 15.V. 1985; vill. Rozhen above Melnik, 30.V.1984. Distribution: South Europe, from France to Bulgaria; Asia Minor. E\SbM\HSbM

Cryptocephalus violaceus Laicharting, 1781

Vihren peak, 2400-2500 m (TOMOV, 1979), vill. Kremen; above Razlog; m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 1200 m (VIG, 2002). New material: Bansko, 1200 m, 10.VI.1987, 12.VI.1972, 30.VI.1969; Melnik, 10.VI.1987; p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 23.VII.1956; m. h. "Banderitsa", 1800 m, 16.VII.1975. Distribution: western, middle and southeastern parts of Europe, from Spain to Ukraine; Asia Minor. E\SbM\HSbM

* *Pachybrachis hieroglyphicus* (Laicharting, 1781)

Bansko, 24.VI.1968, 30.VI.1969, 16.VII.1965; Melnik, 12.VII.1987; vill. Dobrinishte, 17.VII.1965. Distribution: Europe, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Pachybrachis limbatus (Menetries, 1836)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (TOMOV, 1979). New material: Gotse Delchev, 11.V.1968; Melnik, 11.V.1967, 15.V.1985, 23.VI.1969, 7.VII.1988; vill. Mesta, 1.V.1968. Distribution: Balkan countries, Asia Minor, Syria. E\SbM\ESbM

Pachybrachis sinuatus Mulsant, 1859

Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). New material: Bansko, 30.VI.1969; vill. Lilyanovo, 9.V.1968, 11.VII.1965; vill. Mesta, 11.V.1968; Vihren peak, 2050 m, 7.V.1987. Distribution: South France, Mid Europe, Balkan Peninsula, Asia Minor. E\ME

Pachybrachis tessellatus (Olivier, 1791)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (TOMOV, 1979), vill. Dobrinishte (VIG, 2002). New material: Bansko, 5.VI.1985; Melnik, 5.VI.1985, 23.VI.1969; vill. Rozhen, 30.V.1984. Distribution: South and Mid Europe, from North Spain to the Caspian Sea. E\ME

* *Stylosomus tamarisci* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838)

vill. Delchevo, 22.VI.1969. Distribution: Balkan Peninsula, South Ukraine, South Russia. E\SbM\HSbM

Eumolpinae

Bromius obscurus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Bansko (GRUEV, 1992), m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 1200 m (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Europe, the Urals, Siberia, Kazakhstan, Mid and Central Asia, Mongolia, North China, Japan, the Kurils, North America. S\H

Eumolpus asclepiadeus (Pallas, 1776)

Melnik (GRUEV, 1992 - *Chrysochus asclepiadeus*). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, West and Mid Asia, Siberia, Mongolia, North China. S\EAP\SibE

Pachnephorus pilosus (Rossi, 1790)

Pirin Mt. (ROUBAL, 1931), Melnik (WARCZALOWSKI, 1974), Gotse Delchev (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Central and South Europe, West and Mid Asia, Siberia, Mongolia, North China. S\EAP\SibE

Pachnephorus villosus (Duftschmid, 1825)

Melnik; above Kresna, vill. Delchevo (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Southeast Europe, Italy, South France, Caucasus, Turkey, Iran, Syria. E\SbM\HSbM

Chrysomelinae

Chrysolina cerealis alternans (Panzer, 1799)

Gotse Delchev; vill. Mesta (GRUEV, 1992 - *Chrysolina cerealis*). Distribution: Europe (Danube basin; North Balkans). E/SbM/ESbM

Chrysolina fastuosa (Scopoli, 1763)

m. h. "Yane Sandanski"; m. h. "Banderitsa", Gotse Delchev (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Afghanistan, West and Mid Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Chrysolina geminata (Paykull, 1799)

Melnik (WARCZALOWSKI, 1974 - *Chrysomela geminata*), Melnik; m. h. "Banderitsa" (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus. E\ME

Chrysolina gypsophilae (Kuester, 1845)

Melnik (WARCZALOWSKI, 1974 - *Chrysomela gypsophilae*), Melnik; vill. Mesta; p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski (GRUEV, 1992); m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor. E\ME

Chrysolina haemoptera (Linnaeus, 1758)

Melnik; vill. Rozhen nr. Melnik; p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1500 m; Mt. Pirin, 2000 m (GRUEV, 1992), vill. Kremen (VIG, 2002). New material: vill. Lilyanovo, 17.VIII.1979. Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran. E\ME

Chrysolina herbacea (Duftschmid, 1825)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m; p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1400-1600 m (GRUEV, 1978), Melnik; vill. Rozhen nr. Melnik; m. h. "Banderitsa"; Sinanitsa; vill. Vlaha; Gotse Delchev; Bansko, m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski; vill. Lilyanovo; vill. Dobrinishte; Dzhindzhiritsa; Predela-Pass, 1100 m (GRUEV, 1992), Mt. Pirin, 2000 m (GRUEV, 2002b), m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 1200 m; p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, Afghanistan, Pamir, Altai. S\EAP\SibE

Chrysolina hyperici (Forster, 1771)

Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974 - *Chrysomela hyperici*), Melnik, vill. Rozhen nr. Melnik; vill. Dobrinishte; vill. Vlahi; m. h. "Banderitsa" (GRUEV, 1992), vill. Kremen (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Middle Asia (Uzbekistan), North Africa. E\ME

Chrysolina limbata (Fabricius, 1775)

Bansko, 1100 m; Melnik; vill. Baldevo; m. h. "Banderitsa"; p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski (GRUEV, 1992), m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 1200 m (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, West Siberia, Mongolia. S\EAP\SibE

Chrysolina marginata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974 - *Chrysomela marginat*), Melnik; vill. Rozhen nr. Melnik; vill. Dobrinishte; p. "Popski Preslop"; vill. Mesta (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, Afghanistan, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, Siberia (eastwards to Magadan and Khabarovsk), West China, North Africa. S\EAP\TrPal

Chrysolina oricalcia (Mueller, 1776)

p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1500 m (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Asia Minor, Siberia (incl. Maritime Prov.), Mongolia. S\EAP\TrPal

Chrysolina polita (Linnaeus, 1758)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (GRUEV, 1978), Bansko; Melnik; p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1200 m; Predela-Pass (GRUEV, 1992), above Kresna (GRUEV, 2002b). Distribution: Europe, West Siberia, Mongolia, Sakhalien. S\EAP\TrPal

Chrysolina reitteri (Weise, 1884)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m ("*Chrysolina lurida*" - GRUEV, 1978). Distribution: Mid, South and East Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Mid Asia, South Siberia. S\EAP\SSibE

Chrysolina salviae (Germar, 1824)

Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974 - *Crosita salviae*), Melnik (GRUEV, 1992), vill. Lilyanovo; above Kresna (GRUEV, 2002b). Distribution: South Europe northwards to Hungary. E\SbM\HSbM

Chrysolina staphylaea (Linnaeus, 1758)

Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, whole of Siberia, Mongolia, China, Korea. S\EAP\TrPal

Chrysolina turca (Fairmaire, 1865)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 400-450 m (GRUEV, 1978). Distribution: Turkey (European and Asiatic), Bulgaria. SWAs\SbIn\AsM

Chrysolina varians (Schaller, 1783)

Banderitsa Valley (VIG, 2002). New material: Predela-Pass, 29.V.1993. Distribution: Europe, Asia Minor, Siberia, ?Algeria. S\EAP\SibE

Chrysolina vernalis ottomana (Weise, 1906)

above Kresna (GRUEV, 2002b). Distribution: Turkey (European and Asiatic), Balkan Peninsula (Bulgaria, North Greece, Macedonia, Dalmatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Montenegro, Albania). SWAs\SbIn\AsM

Chrysomela populi Linnaeus, 1758

vill. Vlahi (GRUEV, 1992), Sandanski Valley (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Palearctis. S\EAP\HPal

Chrysomela saliceti Suffrian, 1849

p. "Popina laka" above Sandanski, 1300 m (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974 - *Melasoma saliceti*). Distribution: Europe, Kazakhstan, Iran, Mid Asia, Siberia. S\EAP\TrPal

Chrysomela tremulae Fabricius, 1787
p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974 - *Melasoma tremulae*), Bansko, Melnik (GRUEV, 1992), Bistritsa Valley (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Europe, Palaearctic Asia (incl. Japan). S\EAP\TrPal

Chrysomela vigintipunctata (Scopoli, 1763)
Gotse Delchev; Pirinska Bistritsa Valley (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Palaearctic Asia (incl. Japan). S\EAP\TrPal

Colaphus sophiae (Schaller, 1783)
Melnik (GRUEV, 1992 - *Colapbellus sophiae*). Distribution: Europe, Asia Minor. E\ME

Gastrophysa polygoni (Linnaeus, 1758)
Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, Siberia, Mongolia, China, Korea, North Africa. S\EAP\HPal

Gastrophysa viridula (De Geer, 1775)
m. h. "Banderitsa", 1700 m (GRUEV & TOMOV, 1986). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Amurland, Kamchatka. S\EAP\TrPal

Gonioctena fornicata (Brueggemann, 1873)
Melnik; vill. Rozhen nr. Melnik; vill. Mesta (GRUEV, 1992). Known as "Lucerne leaf beetle" (pest). In Bulgaria distributed from the sea coast up to 1200 m or more. Distribution: South Europe, Southeast Europe, southern part of Mid Europe, Asia Minor, Syria. E\SbM\HSbM

Gonioctena pallida reticulata (Bechyne, 1947)
m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski (GRUEV & TOMOV, 1986), m. h. "Yane Sandanski" and p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski (GRUEV, 1990a), Begovitsa Valley (GRUEV, 1992), Mt. Pirin (VIG, 2002). Distribution: mountains of Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria and Montenegro. End\BnEnd

Hydrothassa flavocincta (Brullé, 1832)
p. "Popina laka" above Sandanski, 1200 m (WARCZHALOWKI, 1974), Melnik (GRUEV & TOMOV 1986). Distribution: Balkan Peninsula, Turkey, South Italy. E\SbM\ESbM

Hydrothassa glabra (Herbst, 1783)
vill. Dobrinishte (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Leptinotarsa decemlineata (Say, 1824)
Introduced into Europe from America. In Bulgaria distributed from the sea coast up to 2400 m or more, on Solanaceae. Known as "Potato beetle" (pest)

Oreina speciosissima drenskii (Gruev, 1974)
p. "Bayovi dupki" [locus typicus] (GRUEV, 1974 - *Chrysochloa speciosissima drenskii*). Distribution: Mt. Stara planina (Bulgaria, Serbia), Mt. Rila, Mt. Pirin. End\BnEnd

Oreina virgulata ljubetensis (Apfelbeck, 1912)
vill. Dobrinishte; p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1600 m (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974 - *Chrysochloa virgulata*), m. h. "Banderitsa"; m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski; Predela-Pass (GRUEV, 1990a - *Oreina virgulata*), Bansko; p. "Cherna voda", Bansko (GRUEV, 1992 - *Oreina virgulata*). Distribution: mountains of Macedonia, Serbia, Bulgaria, ?Albania. End\BnEnd

Phaedon armoraciae (Linnaeus, 1758)
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), Begovitsa Valley (GRUEV, 1978), Valyavishki circus; Prevalski circus; Belemeto-circus; Spano pole-circus; Sinanitsa (GUEORGUIEV, 1988), Tevno ezero-Lake; Prevalski-Lakes (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, Siberia. S\EAP\TrPal

Phaedon cochleariae (Fabricius, 1792)

above Sandanski; above Kresna (GRUEV, 1969a), Melnik; p. "Popski Preslop" (GRUEV, 1992), p. "Haramibunar" (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Europe, Palaeartic Asia (incl. tundra). S\EAP\TrPal

Phaedon laevigatus (Duftschmid, 1825)

Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: Mid, South and East Europe. E\ME

Phaedon pyritosus (Rossi, 1792)

Pirin Mt. (ROUBAL, 1931), above Sandanski (GRUEV, 1969a), Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). New material: vill. Rozhen, 30.V.1984. Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, North Africa. S\EAP\SibE

Phratora laticollis (Suffrian, 1851)

p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1400-1600 m (GRUEV, 1978), Melnik; m.h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Palaeartic Asia. S\EAP\TrPal

Phratora tibialis (Suffrian, 1851)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 25-500 m (GRUEV, 1978), Melnik (GRUEV & TOMOV, 1986), Bansko (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Asia Minor. E\ME

Phratora vitellinae (Linnaeus, 1758)

vill. Dobrinishte; Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974 - *Phyllodecta vitellinae*), p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1400-1600 (GRUEV, 1978), Gotse Delchev; Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Palaeartic Asia (excl. Japan). S\EAP\TrPal

Plagiodera versicolora (Laicharting, 1781)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (GRUEV, 1978), Melnik; vill. Rozhen nr. Melnik; above Kresna; vill. Dobrinishte (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Palaeartcis, India, Taiwan. S\EAP\HPal

Plagiosterna aenea (Linnaeus, 1758)

above Kresna (GRUEV, 1992 - *Linacidea aenea*). Distribution: Europe, Palaeartic Asia (incl. Japan). S\EAP\TrPal

Prasocuris junci (Brahm, 1790)

vill. Dobrinishte (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), Gotse Delchev; Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, North Africa. E\ME

Timarcha metallica (Laicharting, 1781)

p. "Popina Laka", above Sandanski, 1500 m (GRUEV, 1992), m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 1200 m (VIG, 2002). Distribution: mountains of Central and South Europe. E\MEMount

Timarcha tenebricosa (Fabricius, 1775)

p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski; Bansko; Vihren peak, 2400 m (GRUEV, 1992), Melnik (GRUEV, 2002b), Bistritsa Valley; ; m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski; Vihren peak, 1800 m (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Mid, South and Southeast Europe, Caucasus. E\ME

Galerucinae

Agelastica alni (Linnaeus, 1758)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (TOMOV, 1979). New material: Melnik, 19.V.1939, 27.IV.1970. Distribution: Europe, from Ireland to South Finland and from the Pyrenees to Caucasus; Asia Minor. E\ME

Calomicrus circumfusus (Marsham, 1802)
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo (TOMOV, 1979 – *Luperus circumfusus*).
New material: Bansko, 8.VI.1961; Melnik, 23.V.1970, 27.V.1984, 8.VI.1961, 16.VI.1978, 23.VI.1969; vill.
Mesta, 11.V.1968; vill. Rozhen, 15.V.1985. Distribution: Europe. E\ME

Calomicrus pinicola (Duftschmid, 1825)
Bansko, 1000-1200 m (TOMOV & GRUEV, 1973 – *Luperus pinicola*), Begovitsa Valley, 1400-1600 m
(TOMOV, 1979 – *Luperus pinicola*), above Razlog (VIG, 2002 – *Luperus pinicola*). New material: Gotse
Delchev, 3.VII.1961; p. “Popina Laka” above Sandanski, 1400-1600 m, 17.VII.1971. Distribution: from
Catalonia and North France to Bulgaria, Dnieper basin and Finland. E\ME

Diorhabda elongata (Brulle, 1832)
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), above railway station Pirin (TOMOV, 1969). New material: vill.
Delchevo, 22.VI.1969, 7.VII.1968, 27.IX.1970. Distribution: Mediterranean, Caucasus, Asia Minor,
Transcaucasus, Middle Asia, Mongolia. S\EAP\SibE

Galeruca interrupta circumdata (Duftschmid, 1825)
vill. Lopovo; Mt. Pirin, Sandanski Valley (VIG, 2002). New material: Melnik, 9.V.1985, 23.VI.1969.
Distribution: Danube basin, Balkan Peninsula, Ukraine. E\SbM\ESbM

* *Galeruca pomonae* (Scopoli, 1763)
Melnik, 14.VI.1985; vill. Rozhen, 14.VI.1985. Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, West Siberia,
North India. S\EAP\SibE

* *Galeruca rufa* Germar, 1824
Melnik, 9.V.1985, 23.V.1970, 27.V.1984, 23.VI.1969, 6.VIII.1984. Distribution: South France, Italy,
Danube basin, Balkan Peninsula, from Ukraine to the basin of lower Volga. E\SbM\HSbM

Galeruca tanaceti (Linnaeus, 1758)
Bistritsa Valley; vill. Lopovo; m. h. “Yane Sandanski” above Sandanski, 1200 m (VIG, 2002). New
material: Melnik, 15.V.1981, 2.VI.1984, 23.VI.1969; vill. Vlaha, 4.VII.1947; vill. Rozhen, 14.VI.1985.
Distribution: from Ireland and Portugal to Korea. S\EAP\TrPal

Galerucella calvariensis (Linnaeus, 1767)
above Razlog (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Siberia, Mongolia,
North China, Japan. S\EAP\TrPal

* *Galerucella lineola* (Fabricius, 1781)
vill. Mesta, 11.V.1968, 18.V.1973; m. h. “Yane Sandanski” above Sandanski, 4.VI.1964. Distribution:
from Ireland to Japan. S\EAP\TrPal

* *Galerucella pusila* (Duftschmid, 1825)
Gotse Delchev, 11.V.1968; Bansko, 24.VI.1968; Melnik, 12.V.1987; vill. Lilyanovo, 11.V.1985; p.
“Popina Laka” above Sandanski, 13.V.1985. Distribution: from Catalonia and the British Isles. To Siberia
and Mongolia. S\EAP\SibE

Lochmaea capreae (Linnaeus, 1758)
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). New material: Gotse Delchev, 11.V.1968; vill. Mesta, 11.V.1968.
Distribution: from Spain and Ireland to North Norway and Japan. S\EAP\TrPal

Luperus cyanipennis Kuester, 1848
p. “Popina Laka” ab. Sandanski (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974 – *Luperus hyperus*; GRUEV & TOMOV, 1975).
New material: Bansko, Melnik, 11.V.1967, vill. Dobrinishte, 13.V.1973, 17.V.1973. Distribution: France,
Italy, Dalmatia, southern part of Mid Europe, Danube basin. E\SbM\HSbM

Luperus flavipes (Linnaeus, 1767)
vill. Dobrinishte, 1300 m (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, North-East Kazakhstan, Siberia, Mongolia. S\EAP\SibE

* *Luperus graecus* Weise, 1886
m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 21.VI.1969. Distribution: Balkan Peninsula. End\BnEnd

* *Luperus viridipennis* Germar, 1824
Pirin Mountain, 4.VIII.1984. Distribution: the Alps, Carpathians, Balkans (mountains), South Ural, Central Asia. S\EAP\SibE

Luperus xanthopoda Schrank, 1781
p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1500 m (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), Begovitsa Valley (TOMOV, 1979). New material: vill. Lilyanovo, 11.VII.1965; m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 21.VI.1969. Distribution: from Iberian Peninsula to Central Asia. S\EAP\SibE

Phyllobrotica adusta (Creutzer, 1799)
Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (TOMOV, 1979), vill. Kremen; p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski (VIG, 2002). New material: Melnik, 15.V.1981, 23.V.1970, 21.VI.1908. Distribution: Mid and South-East Europe. E\ME

Sermylassa balensis (Linnaeus, 1767)
Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (TOMOV, 1979). New material: Bansko, 28.X.1988; vill. Dobrinishte, 17.VI.1965; Banderitsa, 11.VII.1971. Distribution: the great part of Europe; from Kazakhstan and Middle Asia to Altai and Mongolia. S\EAP\SibE

Xanthogalleruca luteola (Mueller, 1766)
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974 - *Galerucella luteola*), Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (TOMOV, 1979 - *Galerucella luteola*), vill. Dobrinishte (VIG, 2002 - *Galerucella luteola*). New material: vill. Lilyanovo, 11.V.1985; p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1250 m, 13.V.1985. Distribution: Europe, Asia Minor, Caucasus, Middle Asia, Iran, North Africa. SWAs\SbIn\InTur

Alticinae

Altica carduorum Guerin-Meneville, 1858
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974 - *Haltica carduorum*), Melnik; Gotse Delchev (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, Siberia, Russian Far East. S\EAP\SibE

Altica impressicollis Reiche, 1862
vill. Mesta (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, Syria, Israel. E\ME

Altica lythri Aube, 1843
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974 - *Haltica ampelophaga*). Distribution: Europe, Turkey. E\ME

Altica oleracea (Linnaeus, 1758)
Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (GRUEV, 1978), Melnik; Gotse Delchev; Mt. Pirin, 1600 m; m. h. "Banderitsa" (GRUEV, 1992), Rozhenski monastery above Melnik (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Europe, Palearctic Asia. S\EAP\TrPal

Altica quercetorum Foudras, 1860
Mt. Pirin (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Turkey. E\ME

- Altica tamaricis* Schrank, 1785
Gotse Delchev; Melnik, vill. Delchevo (GRUEV, 1992), above Kresna (GRUEV, 2002b). Distribution: Europe, Palaearctic Asia (excl. Japan). S\EAP\TrPal
- Aphthona abdominalis* (Duftschmid, 1825)
Melnik, above vill. Hadzhidimovo (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Palaearctic Asia (incl. Japan); North Vietnam. S\EAP\TrPal
- Aphthona cyparissiae* (Koch, 1803)
Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 300-350 m; Banderitsa Valley, 1700-1900 m (GRUEV, 1978), Bansko (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid and South Europe. E\ME
- Aphthona euphorbiae* (Schrank, 1781)
m. h. "Banderitsa" (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Palaearctic Asia eastwards to the southwestern Baikal area, North Africa. S\EAP\SibE
- Aphthona flava* Guillebeau, 1895
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 300-350 m (GRUEV, 1978), Bansko; Melnik; Gotse Delchev (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Central and Southeast Europe westwards to Italy. E\ME
- Aphthona herbigrada* (Curtis, 1837)
Bansko (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, North-West Africa. E\ME
- Aphthona lutescens* (Gyllenhal, 1808)
Bansko (GRUEV, 1992), Melnik; vill. Delchevo (GRUEV, 2002a). Distribution: Europe, Palaearctic Asia eastwards to Transbaikalia (Buryatia), Yemen. S\EAP\SibE
- Aphthona nigriceps* (W. Redtenbacher, 1842)
Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: southern part of Mid Europe, South Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, South Sporades, North-West Africa. E\SbM\HSbM
- Aphthona nigriscutis* Foudras, 1860
Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (GRUEV, 1978). Distribution: Central and South Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Iran, West Kazakhstan, West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE
- Aphthona parnassicola* Heikertinger, 1944
Rozhenski monastery above Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974 - *Aphthona gruszkorum*), Melnik (GRUEV & TOMOV, 1975), Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Greece, Macedonia, southern Bulgaria. End/BnEnd
- Aphthona pygmaea* (Kutschera, 1861)
Melnik; vill. Mesta; m. h. "Banderitsa" (GRUEV, 1992), Bansko, 600 m (GRUEV, 2002a). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Syria, Lebanon, Israel, Yemen, North-East Africa. E\ME
- Aphthona semicyanea* Allard, 1859
Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (GRUEV, 1978). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Transcaucasia, Iran, Syria, Israel, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, West Siberia, Sayan Mts., Altai, Mongolia. S\EAP\SibE
- Aphthona venustula* Kutschera, 1861
Bansko, 1200 m; vill. Dobrinishte; vill. Mesta; Melnik, m. h. "Yane Sandanski", p. "Popski preslop", Banderitsa (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor. E\ME

Batophila moesica Heikertinger, 1948
m. h. "Damyanita"; m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski; m. h. "Vihren"; m. h. "Banderitsa";
Bansko (GRUEV, 1990a). Distribution: mountains of Bulgaria and Romania. E\SEEMount

Batophila rubi (Paykull, 1799)
vill. Dobrinishte (WARCHALOWSKI, 1974), above Sandanski; Bansko (GRUEV, 1992), p. "Popski
preslop"; m. h. "Vihren", 2100 m (GRUEV, 2002), Mt. Pirin (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus,
West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Chaetocnema arida Foudras, 1860
Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid, West and South Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, North-West
Africa. E\ME

* *Chaetocnema concinna* (Marsham, 1802)
Bansko, 18. V. 1978. Distribution: Europe, Palaearctic Asia (excl. Japan), North-West Africa. S\EAP\HPal

Chaetocnema hortensis (Geoffroy, 1785)
above vill. Lilyanovo; vil. Dobrinishte; vill. Rozhen above Melnik; Melnik (GRUEV, 1992), Bansko,
1200 m (GRUEV, 2002b). New material: Rhozhenski monastery, 21.V.1978. Distribution: Europe, Palaearctic
Asia (excl. Japan), Madeira, Saudi Arabia, North-West Africa, Chad, Sudan. S\EAP\HPal

Chaetocnema montenegrina Heikertinger, 1912
Melnik; vill. Dobrinishte; Bansko; vill. Vlahi; m. h. "Banderitsa" (GRUEV, 1992). New material: Rozhenski
monastery, 21.V.1978. Distribution: South-East Europe, Asia Minor, Iran, Afghanistan, Mid Asia.
SWAs\SbIn\InTur

Chaetocnema picipes Stephens, 1831
Bansko (GRUEV, 1992 - *Chaetocnema heikertingeri*). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran,
Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, China, Siberia, Mongolia, Korea. S\EAP\TrPal

Chaetocnema scheffleri (Kutschera, 1864)
Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). New material: Bansko, 18.V.1978. Distribution: southern part of Mid Europe,
East Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, Iraq, Israel, North-West Africa. E\SbM\HSbM

Chaetocnema semicoerulea (Koch, 1803)
vill. Mesta; Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). New material: Rozhenski monastery, 21.V.1978. Distribution: Mid
and South Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, West and Mid Siberia eastwards to Baikal. S\EAP\SibE

Chaetocnema subcoerulea (Kutschera, 1864)
Melnik (BOROWIEC, 1979). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus. E\ME.

Chaetocnema tibialis (Illiger, 1807)
Melnik (WARCHALOWSKI, 1974), Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). New material: Bansko, 18.V.1978.
Distribution: Europe, Palaearctic Asia eastwards to the Baikal area, North Africa. S\EAP\SibE

Crepidodera aurata (Marsham, 1802)
Gotse Delchev; Melnik; m. h. "Banderitsa", 1500 m (GRUEV, 1992). New material: Bansko, 18.V.1978.
Distribution: Europe, Palaearctic Asia (excl. Japan), Morocco. S\EAP\HPal

Crepidodera aurea (Geoffroy, 1785)
vill. Rozhen nr. Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). New material: Bansko, 18.V.1978. Distribution: Europe,
Caucasus, Asia Minor, Cyprus, Iran, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, West Siberia, Transbaikalia. S\EAP\SibE

Crepidodera lamina (Bedel, 1901)
p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1600 m (WARCZALOWSKI, 1974), Melnik (GRUEV, 1992), m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 1200 m (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Europe, Turkey. E\ME

Crepidodera nigricoxis (Allard, 1878)
Melnik; m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski (GRUEV, 1975), vill. Rozhen nr. Melnik (GRUEV, 2002b). New material: Sandanska Bistritsa, 13.V.1983. Distribution: South-East Europe, Caucasus. E\SbM\ESbM

Crepidodera nitidula (Linnaeus, 1758)
p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski (WARCZALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: Europe, West and Mid Siberia, Sayan Mts. S\EAP\SibE

Derocrepis rufipes (Linnaeus, 1758)
southwestern slopes of Vihren peak, 2400-2500 m (GRUEV, 1978), Bansko; Predela-Pass (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, West and Mid Siberia, Sayan Mts. S\EAP\SibE

Dibolia carpathica Weise, 1893
vill. Mesta; above Sandanski (GRUEV, 1979), m. h. "Banderitsa" (GRUEV & TOMOV, 1986), Bansko; track Banderitsa > Bansko (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid, East and South-East Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Israel. S\EAP\SibE

Dibolia cryptocephala (Koch, 1803)
Banderitsa Valley, 1700-1900 m (MOHR, 1981), Melnik (GRUEV, 1978), Bansko (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid and East Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Dibolia depressiuscula (Letzner, 1847)
Melnik (MOHR, 1981). Distribution: Europe, Palaeartic Asia eastwards incl. Baikal area. S\EAP\SibE

Dibolia femoralis Redtenbacher, 1849
Gotse Delchev, above vill. Gospodintsi (GRUEV, 1971), vill. Dobrinishte (WARCZALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Asiatic Turkey, Rhodos. E\ME

Dibolia occultans (Koch, 1803)
Melnik (MOHR, 1981). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, North-West Africa. E\ME

Dibolia timida (Illiger, 1807)
Melnik (GRUEV, 1971; MOHR, 1981). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, North-West Africa. E\ME

Epitrix hirtipennis (Meisheimer, 1847)
Gotse Delchev (GRUEV & BECHEV, 2000). Introduced from America. Pest on Tobacco

Epitrix pubescens (Koch, 1803)
Melnik; vill. Rozhen nr. Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Israel, Asia Minor, Cyprus, Iran, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Hippuriphila modeeri (Linnaeus, 1961)
Melnik; Bansko (GRUEV, 1992), p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1250 m (GRUEV, 2002b). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, all Siberia, Mongolia. S\EAP\TrPal

Longitarsus aeneicollis (Faldermann, 1837)
Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (GRUEV, 1978 - *Longitarsus suturalis*), Melnik; p. "Papaz Chair"; above Sandanski, 800 m (GRUEV, 1992 - *Longitarsus suturalis*). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Syria, Lebanon, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, North-West Africa. E\ME

Longitarsus alferii furthi Gruiev, 1982

Mt. Pirin, 1200 m; Bansko (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Bulgaria, Macedonia, Serbia, Georgia, Crimea, Turkey, Spain, Crete. E\SbM\HSbM

Longitarsus anatolicus Weise, 1900

Melnik (GRUEV & DÖBERL, 2005). Distribution: Iran, Azerbaijan, Asiatic Turkey, Bulgaria, Israel. SWAs\SbIn\InTur

Longitarsus anchusae (Paykull, 1799)

Melnik; Bansko, 1200 m, above vill. Gospodintsi (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, Afghanistan, Iraq, Syria, Jordan, Cyprus, Kazakhstan, Middle Asia, Altai, Siberia (Irkutsk). S\EAP\SibE

Longitarsus apicalis (Beck, 1817)

Mt. Pirin (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1969), vill. Dobrinishte (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), above Bansko (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Canary Islands, Caucasus, West, Mid and South Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Longitarsus ballotae (Marshall, 1802)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (GRUEV, 1978), Melnik; Gotse Delchev; vill. Mesta (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: West, Mid, South and South Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, Cyprus, Syria, Israel, Jordan, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Yemen, North Africa. S\EAP\SSibE

Longitarsus behnei Gruiev et Arnold, 1989

Vihren peak, p. "Kabata", 2600 m – locus typicus (GRUEV & ARNOLD, 1989). Distribution: Bulgaria (Mt. Pirin). End/BgEnd

Longitarsus bertii Leonardi, 1973

above Sandanski (GRUEV, 1971 – *Longitarsus ferrugineus*), Melnik, above vill. Katuntsi (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid, East and South-East Europe, Italy, Caucasus, Turkmenistan, Asia Minor, Iran, Syria, Israel, Cyprus. E\ME

Longitarsus brisouti Heikertinger, 1912

Bansko (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid, South and South-East Europe, Asia Minor. E\ME

Longitarsus brunneus (Duftschmid, 1825)

Bansko (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Palearctic Asia (excl. Japan). S\EAP\TrPal

Longitarsus curtus (Allard, 1860)

Melnik (GRUEV, 1992; WARCZHALOWSKI, 1995). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Afghanistan, Middle Asia, Transbaikalia (Buryatiya). S\EAP\TrPal

Longitarsus exoletus (Linnaeus, 1758)

above Kresna (GRUEV, 1970 – *Longitarsus exoletus rufulus*), Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), above vill. Lilyanovo (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Turkmenistan, Iran, Syria, Cyprus. E\ME

Longitarsus foudrasi Weise, 1893

Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), m. h. "Banderitsa" (GRUEV, 2002b), vill. Lopovo (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Mid and East Europe, Palearctic Asia (excl. Japan), North-West Africa. S\EAP\TrPal

Longitarsus fulgens (Foudras, 1860)

Melnik (BOROWIEC, 1979). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, South Siberia. S\EAP\SSibE

Longitarsus ganglbaueri Heikertinger, 1912
Bansko, 1200 m (GRUEV, 1973a), Mt. Pirin; m. h. “Banderitsa” (GRUEV, 1992), Vihren peak, p. “Kabata” (GRUEV, 2002b). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Mongolia, Siberia, Sakhalien. S\EAP\TrPal

Longitarsus gracilis Kutschera, 1864
vill. Dobrinishte (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Israel, North-West Africa. E\ME

Longitarsus bolsaticus (Linnaeus, 1758)
Gotse Delchev (GRUEV & TOMOV, 1986). Distribution: Europe, Palaearctic Asia. S\EAP\TrPal

Longitarsus kutscherae (Rye, 1872)
Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Palaearctic Asia (excl. Japan), Algeria. S\EAP\HPal

Longitarsus lateripunctatus personatus Weise, 1893
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974 - *Longitarsus lateripunctatus*), Melnik (GRUEV & TOMOV, 1975). Distribution: Mid and East Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Rhodos, Cyprus, Israel. E\ME

Longitarsus linnaei (Duftschmid, 1825)
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), p. “Popina Laka” above Sandanski (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, Syria, Israel. E\ME

Longitarsus longipennis Kutschera, 1863
Melnik; p. “Popina Laka” above Sandanski (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, Siberia eastward to Yakutia. S\EAP\TrPal

Longitarsus luridus (Scopoli, 1763)
Melnik; vill. Mesta; vil. Dobrinishte; Gotse Delchev (GRUEV, 1992), Predela-Pass (GRUEV, 2002b). Distribution: Europe, Palaearctic Asia eastwards to Vladivostok. S\EAP\TrPal

Longitarsus lycopi (Foudras, 1860)
Melnik; p. “Popina Laka” above Sandanski; p. “Popski Preslop” (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, Iraq, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, Syria, Israel, Jordan, Saudi Arabia, Yemen, North Africa, Chad. E\ME

Longitarsus melanocephalus (De Geer, 1775)
vill. Dobrinishte; p. “Popina Laka” above Sandanski (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m; p. “Popina Laka” above Sandanski, 1400-1600 m (GRUEV, 1978), Melnik; Bansko, 1200 m; vill. Dobrinishte; p. “Popski Preslop” (GRUEV, 1992), Predela-Pass (GRUEV, 2002b). Distribution: Europe, Palaearctic Asia eastwards to Transbaikalia. S\EAP\TrPal

Longitarsus membranaceus (Foudras, 1860)
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, Israel, Cyprus, North-West Africa. E\ME

Longitarsus nanus (Foudras, 1860)
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 400-450 m (GRUEV, 1978). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Rhodos, Israel, Algeria. E\ME

Longitarsus niger (Koch, 1803)
vill. Dobrinishte (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), Melnik; Bansko; p. “Popski Preslop”; m. h. “Yane Sandanski” above Sandanski; m. h. “Banderitsa” (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor. E\ME

Longitarsus nigrofasciatus (Goeze, 1777)

above Kresna Gorge (GRUEV, 1969b), Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 400-450 m (GRUEV, 1978), Gotse Delchev; vil. Mesta; Menik; vill. Rozhen nr. Melnik; vill. Dobrinishte; Bansko; m. h. "Vihren", 2100 m (GRUEV, 1992), m. h. "Banderitsa"; m. h. "Banderitsa" > Bansko (GRUEV, 2002b), Mt. Pirin (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Europe, Macaronesia, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Cyprus, North-West Africa, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Longitarsus nimrodi Furth, 1979

Melnik (GRUEV & DÖBERL, 2005). Distribution: North-East Italy, Slovenia, Macedonia, Bulgaria, Turkey, Israel. E/SbM/ESbM

Longitarsus obliteratus (Rosenhauer, 1847)

Melnik (GRUEV, 1969b), p. "Popski Preslop"; vill. Dobrinishte; Melnik; above Kresna (GRUEV, 1973b), Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (GRUEV, 1978). Distribution: Mid, South and South-East Europe, Caucasus, Asiatic Turkey, Iran, Syria, Israel, Jordan. E\ME

Longitarsus pellucidus (Foudras, 1860)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (GRUEV, 1978), Gotse Delchev; Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Palaeartic Asia eastwards to Sayan Mts. and Mongolia; India. S\EAP\SibE

Longitarsus pratensis (Panzer, 1794)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (GRUEV, 1978), p. "Popski Preslop" (GRUEV, 1991), Predela-Pass (GRUEV, 2002b). Distribution: whole of Europe, Palaeartic Asia eastwards to Mid Asia. E\ME

Longitarsus quadriguttatus (Pontoppidan, 1765)

Melnik, Bansko; m. h. "Banderitsa"; p. "Popski Preslop" (GRUEV & TOMOV 1986). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor. E\ME

Longitarsus reichei (Allard, 1860)

Melnik (LEONARDI & DOGUET, 1990). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Iran. E\ME

Longitarsus scutellaris (Rey, 1874)

Rozhenski monastery above Melnik (GRUEV & MERKL, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Siberia, Mongolia. S\EAP\SibE

Longitarsus succineus (Foudras, 1860)

Melnik; p. "Papaz Chair" (GRUEV, 1992), vill. Lilyanovo (GRUEV, 2002b). Distribution: Europe, Palaeartic Asia, North-West Africa. S\EAP\HPal

Longitarsus suturellus (Duftschmid, 1825)

vill. Dobrinishte (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), m. h. "Banderitsa" (GRUEV, 1992), p. "Kabata", 2600 m (GRUEV, 2002b). Distribution: Europe, Palaeartic Asia. S\EAP\TrPal

Longitarsus tabidus (Fabricius, 1775)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (GRUEV, 1978), Melnik; p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, Israel, Cyprus, North-West Africa, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, West Siberia, Sayan Mts., Mongolia. S\EAP\SibE

Lythraria salicariae (Paykull, 1800)

vill. Dobrinishte (GRUEV & TOMOV, 1986). Distribution: Europe, Palaeartic Asia. S\EAP\TrPal

Mantura obtusata (Gyllenhal, 1813)

m. h. "Banderitsa" (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus. E\ME

Minota halmae (Apfelbeck, 1906)
p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski (GRUEV, 1992, 2002a). Distribution: mountains of Central Europe and Northern Balkans. E\MEMount

Mniophila muscorum (Koch, 1803)
Mt. Pirin (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus. E\ME

Neocrepidodera corpulenta (Kutschera, 1860)
p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski (GRUEV, 1992 - *Asiolestia corpulenta*, 2002a). Distribution: Western Alps, Carpathians, mountains of the Balkan Peninsula. E\MEMount

Neocrepidodera ferruginea (Scopoli, 1763)
Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 300-350 m (GRUEV, 1978 - *Crepidodera ferruginea*), Melnik; Bansko; m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski; m. h. "Banderitsa", 1800 m; Predela-Pass (GRUEV, 1992 - *Asiolestia ferruginea*). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Iran. E\ME

Neocrepidodera peirolerii (Kutschera, 1860)
Kamenitsa peak, 2000 m (WARCHALOWSKI, 1974 - *Crepidodera peirolerii*), Begovitsa Valley, 1900-2000 m (GRUEV, 1978 - *Crepidodera peirolerii*). "Popina Laka" (GRUEV, 1990a - "*Asiolestia peirolerii*", 2002a). Distribution: mountains of Austria, Slovenia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Macedonia, Bulgaria, France, North Italy, Switzerland. E\MEMount

Neocrepidodera transversa (Marsham, 1802)
Melnik; Gotse Delchev (GRUEV, 1992 - *Asiolestia transversa*). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, Cyprus. E\ME

Phyllotreta astrachanica Lopatin, 1977
Gotse Delchev; Melnik; Bansko (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Cyprus, North-West Kazakhstan. E\ME

Phyllotreta atra (Fabricius, 1775)
Melnik; vill. Rozhen nr. Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). New material: Bansko, 18.V.1978. Distribution: Europe, Palearctic Asia (excl. Japan), Morocco, Yemen. S\EAP\HPal

Phyllotreta balcanica Heikertinger, 1909
Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). New material: Rozhenski monastery, 21.V.1978; Bansko, 18.V.1978. Distribution: South and South-East Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Afghanistan, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia. SWAs\SbIn\InTur

Phyllotreta cruciferae (Goeze, 1777)
Melnik (WARCHALOWSKI, 1974), Begovitsa Valley, 1900-2000 m; Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (GRUEV, 1978), Melnik; Gotse Delchev (GRUEV, 1992). New material: Bansko, 18.V.1978. Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, West Siberia, Sayan Mts., Mongolia, Israel, Jordan, North Africa, Ethiopia, Sudan, India. S\EAP\SibE

* *Phyllotreta diademata* Foudras, 1860
ab. vill. Vlaha, 15.VI.1970. Distribution: throughout Europe to Central Asia, recorded also from North India (Sikkim). S\EAP\SibE

Phyllotreta nemorum (Linnaeus, 1758)
vill. Rozhen nr. Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Palearctic Asia (excl. Japan). S\EAP\SibE

Phyllotreta nigripes (Fabricius, 1775)
Melnik; vill. Delchevo; m. h. "Vihren", 2100 m (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Palearctic Asia eastwards to Middle Asia and Kazakhstan, North Africa. E\ME

Phyllotreta ochripes (Curtis, 1837)

Melnik (GRUEV, 1992), above Kresna (GRUEV, 2002b). Distribution: Europe, Palearctic Asia (excl. Japan). S\EAP\TrPal

Phyllotreta procera (Redtenbacher, 1849)

Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Macaronesia, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, Mid Asia, Israel, Jordan, Cyprus, North-West Africa, Tanzania. SWAs\SbIn\InTur

Phyllotreta punctulata (Marshall, 1802)

Melnik (GRUEV, 1992 - *Phyllotreta aerea*). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Israel, Morocco. E\ME

Phyllotreta striolata (Fabricius, 1803)

m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski (GRUEV & TOMOV, 1965 - *Phyllotreta vittata*). Distribution: Europe, Asia, Indonesia. S\EAP\TrPal

Phyllotreta tetrastigma (Comolli, 1837)

Mt. Pirin (GRUEV & TOMOV, 1986), m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski; p. "Papaz Chair" (GRUEV, 1992), p. "Bazovitsa" (GRUEV, 2002b). Distribution: Europe, Turkey, West and Mid Siberia, Yakutia. S\EAP\SibE

Phyllotreta vilis Weise, 1888

Melnik (TOMOV & GRUEV, 1973). Distribution: Southeast Europe, Turkey E\SbM\ESbM

Phyllotreta vittula (Redtenbacher, 1849)

Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 300-350 m (GRUEV, 1978), Melnik; Melnik > vill. Rozhen (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Palearctic Asia (excl. Japan). S\EAP\TrPal

Podagrica fuscicornis (Linnaeus, 1766)

Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1200 m (GRUEV, 2002b), Sandanska Bistritsa Valley (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Syria, Israel, Lebanon, North-West Africa, Canary Islands. E\ME

Podagrica malvae (Illiger, 1807)

Melnik; vill. Rozhen nr. Melnik; p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1700 m (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, Iraq, Syria, Jordan, Israel, Cyprus. E\ME

Podagrica menetriesi (Faldermann, 1837)

Melnik; m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Rhodos, Iraq, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, West China. SWAs\SbIn\InTur

Psylliodes aereus austriacus Heikertinger, 1911

Vihren peak, 2400 m (GRUEV & TOMOV, 1998; GRUEV, 2002a). Distribution: mountains of Austria, Bulgaria, Czechia, Slovakia, Ukraine, Hungary, Romania. E\MEMount

Psylliodes affinis (Paykull, 1799)

Bansko; vill. Lilyanovo (GRUEV, 1992), p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski, 1250 m (GRUEV, 2002b). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, West Siberia, Altai, Morocco. S\EAP\SibE

Psylliodes chalcomerus (Illiger, 1807)

Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). New material: Bansko, 18.V.1978; Rozhenski monastery nr. Melnik. Distribution: Europe, Palearctic Asia (excl. Japan), North-West Africa. S\EAP\HPal

Psylliodes circumdatus (Redetenbacher, 1842)
Melnik; vill. Rozhen nr. Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Iran, Near East, North Africa. E\ME

Psylliodes cupreus (Koch, 1803)
Melnik; vill. Rozhen nr. Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). New material: Bansko, 18.V.1978. Distribution: Europe, Palearctic Asia eastwards to Transbaikalia, North-West Africa. S\EAP\SibE

Psylliodes dulcamarae (Koch, 1803)
p. "Popina Laka" above Sandanski (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974), vill. Lilyanovo, 600 m (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Palearctic Asia eastwards to West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Psylliodes hyoscyami (Linnaeus, 1758)
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: Europe, Palearctic Asia (excl. Japan). S\EAP\TrPal

Psylliodes instabilis Feudras, 1860
Gotse Delchev (GRUEV, 1992), Melnik (GRUEV, 2002b). Distribution: Mid and South Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Israel, Cyprus, North-West Africa. E\ME

Psylliodes isatidis Heikertinger, 1912
Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Palearctic Asia eastwards to Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, West Siberia and Mongolia. S\EAP\SibE

Psylliodes kiesewetteri Kutschera, 1864
Melnik (WARCZHALOWSKI, 1974 - *Psylliodes glabra*), Bansko (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: South-East Europe, Italy, Austria, Asia Minor. E\SbM\ESbM

Psylliodes laticollis Kutschera, 1864
Melnik (GRUEV, 1990b). Distribution: Mid, West and South Europe, North-West Africa, Macaronesia. E\ME

Psylliodes napi (Fabricius, 1792)
Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Palearctic Asia (excl. Japan), North-West Africa. S\EAP\HPal

Psylliodes pallidicolor Pic, 1903
Sandanski > vill. Lilyanovo, 250-500 m (GRUEV, 1978). New material: Melnik, VIII.1982. Distribution: Bulgaria, Greece, Spain, Asiatic Turkey, Iraq, Israel, Lebanon, Syria. M\HM

Hispinac

Hispa atra Linnaeus, 1767
Melnik; vill. Dobrinishte (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Palearctic Asia eastwards to North China; North Africa. S\EAP\SibE

Cassidinae

Cassida atrata Fabricius, 1787
vill. Dobrinishte (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid and South-East Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor. E\ME

Cassida fastuosa Schaller, 1783
Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid, South and Eastern Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Mid Asia, West Siberia. S\EAP\SibE

Cassida ferruginea Goeze, 1777
Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Siberia eastwards to the Baikal area. S\EAP\SibE

Cassida flaveola Thunberg, 1794
m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 1230 m (GRUEV, 1967), vill. Lilyanovo, p. "Popski preslop" (GRUEV, 1992), vill. Rozhen nr. Melnik (GRUEV, 2002a). Distribution: Europe, Palaeartic Asia eastwards to the Russian Far East. S\EAP\TrPal

Cassida lineola Creutzer, 1799
Melnik (WARCZALOWSKI, 1974), above Kresna (GRUEV & TOMOV, 1986), Melnik > vill. Hotovo (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Palaeartic Asia. S\EAP\TrPal

Cassida margaritacea Schaller, 1783
Melnik; vill. Dobrinishte (GRUEV, 1992), Rozhenski monastery above Melnik (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Siberia eastwards to the Baikal area. S\EAP\SibE

Cassida murraea Linnaeus, 1767
vill. Delchevo (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Palaearticis (excl. North Africa). S\EAP\TrPal

Cassida nobilis Linnaeus, 1758
Melnik (WARCZALOWSKI, 1974). Distribution: Europe, Palaeartic Asia (incl. Japan). S\EAP\TrPal

Cassida pannonica Suffrian, 1844
Melnik; vill. Mesta (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Mid, South and East Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, North Kazakhstan, Middle Asia. SWAs\SbIn

Cassida panzeri Weise, 1907
Predela-Pass (GRUEV & TOMOV, 1986). Distribution: From Mid and East Europe to the Russian Far East and Japan. S\EAP\TrPal

Cassida prasina Illiger, 1798
Melnik; Predela-Pass, m. h. "Yane Sandanski", Banderitsa, Sandanska Bistritsa (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Asia Minor, Kazakhstan, Siberia, North China, Taiwan. S\EAP\SibE

Cassida rubiginosa Mueller, 1776
above Kresna; vill. Dobrinishte; m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 1250 m; m. h. "Banderitsa" (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Palaearticis, Taiwan. S\EAP\HPal

Cassida sanguinolenta Mueller, 1776
Melnik; m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski (GRUEV, 1992), Rozhenski monastery above Melnik (VIG, 2002). Distribution: Europe, Palaeartic Asia eastwards to Kamchatka. S\EAP\TrPal

Cassida seladonia Gyllenhal, 1827
Melnik (GRUEV & TOMOV, 1986). Distribution: Mid, South and Eastern Europe, Precaucasus, North-West Africa. E\ME

Cassida subferruginea Schrank, 1776
Melnik; vill. Mesta (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Palaearticis. S\EAP\TrPal

Cassida subreticulata Suffrian, 1844
Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asia Minor, Turkmenistan, Iran, Siberia (with Amurland). S\EAP\SibE

Cassida vibex Linnaeus, 1767
Melnik (GRUEV, 1992). Distribution: Europe, Palaeartic Asia. S\EAP\TrPal

Cassida viridis Linnaeus, 1758
vill. Lilyanovo; m. h. "Yane Sandanski" above Sandanski, 1250 m; p. "Popski Preslop" (GRUEV, 1992).
Distribution: Palaeartcis. S\EAP\HPal

Zoogeography

Biogeographically the Pirin Mountain belongs to three regions (GRUEV, 1988): Mountainous (Rila-Rhodopes subregion – nearly above 900-1000 m a. s. l.), Mid-Bulgarian (Upper-Struma subregion – below 900-1000 m a. s. l.) and South Bulgarian (Struma-Mesta subregion – below 900-1000 m a. s. l.). The differences in conditions in those parts of the mountain (climate, relief, petrographic characteristics, ground, etc.) stipulate the diversity of the flora and vegetation and the fauna and animal populations. Thus, worm-loving forms inhabit the low parts of the mountain, the cool- and cold-loving forms – the higher parts, and the forms with large ecological possibilities – all the zones.

The zoogeographical belonging of the taxa (see Faunistic list) are presented mainly after the works of GRUEV (1988, 1990, 2000, 2002, 2002a), GRUEV (In: GRUEV & KUZMANOV, 1994, 1999), GRUEV (1995) and GRUEV & BECHEV (2000):

1. S – Siberian complex
 - EAP – Euro Asiatic Palaeartic element
 - SibE – Sibero-European subelement
 - SSibE – Southsibero-European subelement
 - TrPal – Transpalaeartic subelement
 - HPal – Holopalaeartic subelement
 - H – Holarctic element
2. E – European complex
 - ME – Mid European element
 - MEMount – Mid European mountain element
 - SEEMount – Southeast European mountain element
 - SbM – Sub Mediterranean element
 - HSbM – Holosubmediterranean subelement
 - ESbM – Eastsubmediterranean subelement
3. M – Mediterranean complex
 - HM – Holomediterranean element
4. SWAs – Southwest Asiatic complex
 - SbIn – Sub Iranian element
 - InTur – Irano-Turanian subelement
 - AsM – Asia Minor subelement
5. End – Endemic
 - BnEnd – Endemic of the Balkan Peninsula
 - BgEnd – Endemic of Bulgaria

The Siberian (150 taxa) and the European (113 taxa) complexes are the dominant zoogeographical complexes in the Pirin Mountain. Their components are represented in various zones, and some species of high ecological valence are distributed from foot to peak.

The taxa of the Siberian complex, arranged by rate of richness, are: Sibero-European (incl. 11 Southsibero-European) - 83, Transpalaeartic - 52, Holopalaeartic - 14, Holarctic - 1. The taxa of the European complex are: Mid European - 77, Mideuropean mountainous - 5, Holosubmediterranean - 13, Eastsubmediterranean - 17, Southeast European mountainous - 1.

The sub Mediterranean forms, distributed in the Sub Mediterranean zone (GRUEV, 2000) of Eurasia (and also in the Mediterranean: North, East or the whole), and the Mediterranean species (Holomediterranean - 2), are established in the low warm parts of the Pirin Mountain

The five representatives of the Mideuropean mountain element, and also one species of the Southeast European mountain element (*Batophila moesica* - with probably South Carpathian origin) are found in the Pirin Mountain between 1200 and 2400 m a. s. l.

The Southwest Asiatic complex is represented by only 15 species (Sub Iranian - 5, Asia Minor - 3, Irano-Turanian - 7), established mostly in the low parts, and one - from Melnik up to Bansko.

The group of the endemics consists of 7 taxa. The subspecies *Gonioctena pallida reticulata*, *Oreina speciosissima drenskii* and *O. virgulata ljubetensis* are Balkan mountain neoendemics of glacial origin from mid European mountain ancestor forms. The Balkan endemics *Clytra valeriana tetrastigma*, *Luperus graecus* and *Aphthona parmassicola* are probably of Sub Mediterranean or Mideuropean origin dating back to the warmer times of the late Tertiary. The Bulgarian endemic *Longitarsus behnei* is found in the alpine zone of the Pirin Mountain, in June, by snow edges. That species was described not long ago. So, for the time being it has to be considered as an endemic of the Pirin Mountain only conditionally. Perhaps *L. behnei* is a Quaternary derivative of a hypothetical Mid European mountain form

Some taxa are excluded from the herein presented zoogeographical review because of their unclear zoogeographic belonging. A few other species are treated here under different zoogeographical types (compared with those in GRUEV & BECHEV, 2000) after newly established data about them.

The role of the Pirin Mountain as a refugium complex has been accentuated many times by the botanists and zoologists. There are many plants and animals surviving in the Pirin refugia, and many new taxa have been formed in the mountain. The endemics and the rare mountain species of Chrysomelidae enumerated here illustrate that particular role of the Pirin Mountain too. There is no danger of their populations being injured because the high mountain vegetation, including the food plants of the leaf beetles, is unaffected for the time being.

The leaf beetles, especially the species of *Chrysolina* and *Oreina*, contribute to the common beauty of the Pirin Mountain with their many-coloured tint of body.

Acknowledgements

I deeply thank Dr. Vassil Tomov from the University of Plovdiv for the loan and determination of his material of Orsodacninae, Donaciinae, Criocerinae, Clytrinae, Cryptocephalinae and Galerucinae.

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Received: 26.04.2005

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Листоядите (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) на Пирин планина

Благой ГРУЕВ

(Резюме)

Направен е фаунистичен и зоогеографски преглед на листоядите на Пирин. Общият брой на установените до момента таксони е 289 (включително 38, съобщени тук за първи път за фауната на Пирин). Този брой съставлява 57 % от всички установени в България видове и подвидове листояди. От тях 6 са балкански ендемити (*Clytra valeriana tetrastigma*, *Luperus graecus*, *Gonioctena pallida reticulata*, *Oreina speciosissima drenskii*, *O. virgulata ljubetensis*, *Aphthona parnassicola*), а един - български (пирински) ендемит (*Longitarsus behnei*). Преобладаващи зоогеографски комплекси са Сибирският (150 таксона) и Европейският (113 таксона). Установени са и 15 представители на Югозападноазиатския комплекс и 2 на Медитеранския комплекс (Холомедитерански видове: *Miopristis dentipes* и *Psylliodes pallidicolor*).

Еберхард Унджиян на 70 години

Алекси ПОПОВ

Неотдавна навърши 70-годишна възраст Еберхард Унджиян, чието име свързваме със зоологическите му изследвания, с активната му природозащитна дейност в Русенския край и с дългогодишните му усилия да осигури по-добри условия за развитието на отдел Природа на регионалния музей в Русе. Той е роден на 7 юли 1934 в Берлин в семейството на арменец и германка. В началото на 1944 семейството се преселва от Майсен в България и младият Еберхард завършва френски колеж и гимназия, а през 1958 и биология в Софийския университет със специализация към Катедрата по зоология на гръбначните животни. За кратко време е учител в Образцов чифлик край Русе и работи в Института по рибарство във Варна. Цялата му по-нататъшна професионална биография преминава като завеждащ отдел Природа на Регионалния исторически музей в Русе, какъвто е в продължение на 34 години (1960-1994). Сега е пенсионер, а през

1996-1999 е бил експерт по биологични въпроси при Дирекцията на Природния парк Русенски Лом.

Научната му дейност, плод на която са 20 статии и книги, е посветена на гръбначните животни. Многогодишните си наблюдения в долината на Ломовете и природния парк, безспорно най-интересната част от природата в Русенско, той обобщава в седем книги и статии, посветени на бозайниците, птиците, влечугите, земноводните и рибите. Е. Унджиян е открил речния ивъркач като нова птица за българската фауна и е намерил за първи път в Русенско обикновения буревестник и трипръстата чайка от птиците, както и змигуцера и гекона от влечугите.

Зоолозите от неговото поколение го познават като човек с широка биологична култура и ревностен популяризатор на природонаучни знания. Автор е на около 120 научнопопулярни статии, от които 20 в Природа и знание и други списания. Те са посветени на видове бозайници и птици, мекотели и насекоми, на сунавските острови, на препарирането на едри животни. Владенето или ползването на основните чужди езици му помага да състави нетезичен речник на птиците в Европа и шестезичен речник на дърветата и храстите в България, които макар и непубликувани, са на разположение на българската общественост съответно в Българското дружество за защита на птиците и в Дирекцията на Природния парк Русенски Лом. В продължение на десет години той реферира в Орнитологическия информационен бюлетин 58 чуждестранни публикации върху българските птици. Ръководи пет полета практики с германски и български студенти в Северна България.

Докато завеждаше отдел Природа, Еберхард Унджиян неуморно се бореше за разрешаване на въпроса с останалия без сграда отдел на музея. Той състави план за експозицията и през всичките тези години успя да опази колекциите, чийто родоначалник е първият изследовател на фауната и флората на Русенско – учителят Васил Ковачев. Сега мечтата на Е. Унджиян е на път да се осъществи. В нова сграда са приютени колекциите и препараторската работилница. Остава да се достроят залите за бъдещата експозиция.

За интензивната си дейност по изследване на пещерите Еберхард Унджиян е награден от Българския туристически съюз с медал Алеко Константинов и от Българската федерация по спелеология със сребърен и бронзов прилеп.

Българските зоолози пожелават на Еберхард Унджиян в добро здраве да продължи толкова актуалната и полезна за нашето общество природозащитна дейност.